

First survey of myxomycetes in successional and mangrove forests of Negros Oriental, Philippines

Anton Raphael U. Lim¹, Romeo Manuel N. Silva¹, Gabriel Renzo E. Lesaca¹, Vanessa Joy C. Mapalo², Melissa H. Pecundo³ and Thomas Edison E. dela Cruz^{1,2}

¹Department of Biological Sciences, College of Science, University of Santo Tomas, España Blvd. 1008 Manila, Philippines

²Fungal Biodiversity, Ecogenomics and Systematics (FBeS) Group, Research Center for the Natural and Applied Sciences, University of Santo Tomas, España Blvd. 1008 Manila, Philippines

³Fairy Lake Botanical Garden, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Shenzhen 518004, China

E-mail: tedelacruz@ust.edu.ph

Received: 15 June 2021

Accepted for publication: 9 July 2021

Published: 13 July 2021

Assigned editor: Carlos Rojas

Abstract: Plant-based substrates from two mangrove forests and two woodlands or successional forests in Negros Oriental, Philippines were used to prepare moist chamber cultures to survey for myxomycetes. A total of 19 species and 12 genera were identified from moist chamber cultures of samples collected from the successional forests while five species and genera were recorded from the coastal mangrove forests. Pooling together the number of identified species, three were recorded as abundant in Negros Oriental while two species were common, eight were occasional, and six were rare. *Didymium nigripes*, *Stemonitis fusca* and *Diderma effusum* were among the most abundant species in this province. We also report for the first time five species of myxomycetes, namely, *Didymium nigripes*, *Lamproderma scintillans*, *Arcyria cinerea*, *Stemonitis fusca*, and *Physarum oblatum*, from mangrove forests in the Philippines.

Keywords: inland forests, mangroves, slime molds, taxonomic diversity, woodlands

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

Introduction

The Visayas region of the Philippines consists of several major islands (i.e., Panay, Negros, Cebu, Bohol, Leyte, and Samar) and more than 300 smaller islands, all located in the central part of the Philippine archipelago. Among the major islands, Negros Island is considered the second largest with a land area of 12 705 km² and is divided geographically and administratively into two provinces, Negros Occidental (northwestern half) and Negros Oriental (southeastern half), by a range of rugged mountains. Much of the island's geography is covered by sugarcane plantation, its main crop since the Spanish colonial era. Thus, much of the original flora and fauna of the island has been confined to the mountainous areas, which are not conducive for sugarcane growth, and/or to isolated nature reservations scattered across the island. This current environmental scenario offers an opportunity to study species diversity of microorganisms, particularly the myxomycetes, between isolated nature reserves.

Myxomycetes are a group of fungus-like protists that are widely distributed in terrestrial habitats and are usually associated with decaying plant materials teeming with bacteria and other decomposing microorganisms, on which they feed. Their life cycle is characterized by the formation of acellular plasmodia and the development of spore-bearing sporocarps. Previous studies have shown their potential contribution as model organism to elucidate various cellular processes, a candidate for bioremediating toxic metals (Rea-Maminta *et al.* 2015), as producer of extracellular enzymes (Macabago and dela Cruz 2014), and as an important source of biofuel (Tran *et al.* 2015). However, despite the increasing number of studies that were conducted in the Philippines, there is still limited information on these organisms in many island ecosystems in the country. In fact, studies of myxomycetes in the Visayas region, home to six of the ten largest islands in the country, are relatively few.

The first study of myxomycetes in the region focused only on the province of Negros Occidental in the Negros Island, which generally compared the assemblages of myxomycetes in the mountainous forest of Mt. Kanlaon and the monotypic agricultural sugarcane plantation (Alfaro *et al.* 2014). Their findings recorded 28 species, with the mountain forests reporting the greatest number of species than agricultural plantation, as expected. This study compiled evidence showing that a habitat with more heterogeneous plant communities can yield a higher number of species than a habitat dominated by a single plant. In another study within the region, the diversity of ground-litter inhabiting myxomycetes were also assessed in seven different study sites along a disturbance gradient in Bohol Islands (Macabago *et al.* 2017). The seven study sites included grassland, indigenous woodland, monotypic plantation, heterogonous forest, coastal mixed forest, reef woodland, and islet mixed forest. A total of 54 myxomycetes were identified in the study with the most diverse being recorded in the coastal mixed forest site. This study also suggested the influence of disturbances in the spore dispersal of myxomycetes in different disturbed habitats.

In contrast, many island ecosystems in the Luzon region located in the northern part of the Philippines were already covered by several surveys and detailed ecological studies. Myxomycetes have been reported in Lubang Island, Occidental Mindoro with 45 species of myxomycetes, six of which were new records in the country (Macabago *et al.* 2012), in Puerto Galera, Oriental Mindoro with 42 species of myxomycetes collected from inland lowland mountain forests and coastal forests (Dagamac *et al.* 2015a), in Polilio Island, Quezon Province with 34 species (Viray *et al.* 2015), in Coron Island, Palawan with 25 species obtained from coast and inland forests of the island (Macabago *et al.* 2020a), and in Caramoan Islands, Bicol region with 38 species of myxomycetes collected from four different islands with varying distance and sizes (Macabago *et al.* 2020b). The assemblages of myxomycetes in two lowland mountain forests – Mt Malasimbo in Puerto Galera, Oriental Mindoro, and Mt Siburan in Sablayan, Occidental Mindoro were also compared by Pecundo *et al.* (2020). All these studies demonstrate the enormous taxonomic diversity of myxomycetes in many large and small island ecosystems. Thus, to contribute significantly to the growing trend of documenting assemblages of myxomycetes in the Philippine islands, the present study recorded the species of myxomycetes in two distinct habitats, a mangrove forest and a man-maintained woodland or successional forest, in the province of Negros Oriental within the island of Negros. The study is also the first attempt to explore myxomycetes from mangrove ecosystems in the Philippines which covers more than 250,000 hectares in the whole archipelago (Long and Giri 2011).

Materials and methods

Study Sites

A sampling expedition was conducted in the province of Negros Oriental located at the southeastern side of Negros Island in July 2017. Two successional forests, here also reported as woodlands, and two coastal mangrove forests were chosen as collecting localities. These study sites were: (1) Liptong Woodland (LP, 9°15.684'N; 123°14.515'E), a 1-hectare forest patch and reservation in the municipality of Bacong, (2) Ayungon Forest (AY, 9°50.502'N; 123°2.642'E), a successional forest in the municipality of Ayungon, (3) Tanjay mangrove forest (TJ, 9°32.883'N; 123°9.148'), a reforestation site for mangroves located along the coast in the city of Tanjay, and (4) Tinaogan mangrove forest (TG, 9°47.844'N; 123°8.785'E), a coastal mangrove forest in the municipality of Bindoy (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Collecting localities in Negros Oriental, Philippines. The successional forests or woodlands in Ayungon and Liptong are marked by black dots while the coastal mangrove forest sites in Tinaogan and Tanjay are marked by red dots.

Substrate Collection and Moist Chamber Preparation

For the woodlands, three collecting sites were initially identified for the collection of substrata. In each one of these sites, ten samples each of aerial leaf litter (AL), ground leaf litter (GL), and twigs (TW) were collected resulting to a total of 90 samples for Liptong woodland and 90 samples for the Ayungon successional forest. For the coastal mangrove forests, only one collecting site was studied per location, from which 10 samples each of bark (BK), ground litter (GL), and twigs (TW) were collected for a total of 30 samples for each collecting locality. Each sample was prepared as a single moist chamber (n=240).

The moist chambers (i.e., disposable plastic petri dishes fitted with paper towels) were lined with substrates which were cut into small pieces, then flooded overnight with tap water, the pH determined, and the excess water poured out. The moist chambers were placed in a cabinet away from direct sunlight and checked every week for the presence of plasmodia or sporocarps until the 8th week. Sporocarps with its substrata were collected and pasted in match box-sized small cardboard boxes for specimen storage and species identification.

Species Identification and Data Analysis

Collected identifiable sporocarps were observed with a dissecting microscope (Best Scope BS-3040) and its spore morphologies were determined using a light microscope (Olympus CX31-12C04). Morphological characteristics such as size, stalk length, color, shape of the hypothallus, and ornamentation of the spores were used to determine the identity of the species. To prepare the slide for spore morphology, the spore mass was carefully removed using stainless steel tweezers and placed on a glass slide. Then, a drop of 95% Ethanol was added to the material and allowed to dry. Afterwards, a drop of 3% potassium hydroxide was placed to allow the spores and other structures to expand (Stephenson and Stempen 1994). A cover slide was placed on top of the specimen and gently pressed to allow the spore mass to break for characterization of the spores. The morphometric data were compared with descriptions published in the Eumycetozoa Project (<http://www.discoverlife.org>) and other sites devoted to slime molds (e.g., <http://hiddenforest.co.nz/slime/index.htm>), and from descriptions in Leontyev (2010). Nomenclature was verified using an updated web-based reference site (<http://eumycetozoa.com>).

Moist chamber productivity was measured in accordance with the calculation of Dagamac et al. (2012). Positive records are moist chambers with the recorded presence of plasmodia and/or sporocarps. The percent yield was computed by dividing the number of positive moist chambers over the total number of prepared moist chambers multiplied by 100. The number of records, species and genera was accounted for each collecting locality, from which the taxonomic diversity index (TDI), also known as the S/G ratio, was computed as the ratio between the number of species and the number of genera. The number of shared and exclusive myxomycetes was also determined and expressed as a Venn diagram. The number of records was pooled for all collecting sites and used to compute for the relative abundance which was expressed as the number of records per species over the total number of records. We then used the Abundance Index (AI) developed by Dagamac et al. (2012) which was based on a smaller number of records (n=159) as similarly observed in this study (n=62). This AI was previously used in the study of Policina and dela Cruz (2020a, 2020b) to assess abundance of a very specialized guild of myxomycetes. Thus, AI values are R = rare, if the number of specimens (abundance) of a particular species is <3% of the total number of collections, O = occasional, if the abundance is $\geq 3\%$ but <5% of the total number of collections, C = common, if the abundance is $\geq 5\%$ but <10% of the total number of collections, and A = abundant, if the abundance is $\geq 10\%$ of the total number of collections.

Results

Our study recovered a total of 62 identifiable sporocarps from 240 moist chamber cultures. We identified these sporocarps as belonging to 19 species, 12 genera, six families, and four orders of myxomycetes (Table 1). Higher myxomycete records and species richness were significantly recorded in woodlands (forest patch) or successional forest sites than in coastal mangrove forest sites. Specifically, both successional forests recorded 13 species and nine genera as opposed to 3-4 species and genera in

mangrove forests. The overall TDI, calculated as S/G ratio, for the general sampling site in Negros Oriental is 1.6. The two successional forest sites, AY and LP, showed a TDI of 1.4. The TDI for the coastal mangrove sites was not determined due to the few number of recovered taxa. It maybe clear from the sporocarp collections that the woodlands or successional forests were species rich, and expectedly, were more diverse than the coastal mangrove ecosystems. However, when we normalized the data and accounted for the number of recorded individuals and species per MC, our computations showed the successional forests with a proportion of 0.2-0.4 records/MC and 0.14 species/MC had closer values to the coastal mangrove sites with a proportion of 0.1 records/MC and 0.13 species/MC.

Table 1. Number and relative abundance of myxomycetes collected from successional and mangrove forests in Negros Oriental, Philippines.

Species name	Successional Forests		Mangrove Forests		Overall	Relative Abundance ^b
	AY ^a	LP	TJ	TG		
<i>Arcyria afroalpina</i>	1	0	0	0	1	R
<i>Arcyria cinerea</i>	0	4	1	1	6	C
<i>Arcyria globosa</i>	1	1	0	0	2	O
<i>Arcyria incarnata</i>	1	1	0	0	2	O
<i>Collaria arcyrionema</i>	1	4	0	0	5	C
<i>Craterium minutum</i>	0	1	0	0	1	R
<i>Cribraria microcarpa</i>	2	0	0	0	2	O
<i>Diachea leucopodia</i>	0	2	0	0	2	O
<i>Diderma effusum</i>	1	7	0	0	8	A
<i>Didymium iridis</i>	1	0	0	0	1	R
<i>Didymium nigripes</i>	2	7	0	1	10	A
<i>Didymium squamulosum</i>	0	2	0	0	2	O
<i>Hemitrichia calyculata</i>	1	0	0	0	1	R
<i>Lamproderma scintillans</i>	0	2	0	1	3	O
<i>Licea operculata</i>	1	0	0	0	1	R
<i>Physarum album</i>	1	0	0	0	1	R
<i>Physarum echinosporum</i>	0	2	0	0	2	O
<i>Physarum oblatum</i>	1	1	1	0	3	O
<i>Stemonitis fusca</i>	5	2	1	1	9	A
Total number of records	19	36	3	4	62	
Number of genera	9	9	3	4	12	
Number of species	13	13	3	4	19	
Taxonomic diversity index (TDI)	1.4	1.4	-	-	1.6	

^aStudy sites: AY = Ayungon successional forest, LP = Liptong woodland or forest patch, TJ = Tanjay mangrove forest, TG = Tinaogan mangrove forest

^bAbundance index: A = abundant if RA is $\geq 10\%$, C = common if RA is $\geq 5\%$ but $< 10\%$, O = occasional if RA is $\geq 3\%$ but $< 5\%$, R = rare if RA is $< 3\%$

Based on the AI, three species were classified as abundant, two as common, eight as occasional, and six as rare. Some representative myxomycete specimens collected in our study are shown in Fig. 2. The shared and unique or exclusive taxa between the woodlands or successional forest sites and the mangrove forest sites are shown in Fig. 3. Between the two successional forest sites (AY and LP), seven

myxomycetes species were shared whereas each forest site showed six exclusive species. Two species were shared between the mangrove forest sites while one and two species were exclusive to TJ and TG, respectively. We observed only one species, *Stemonitis fusca*, across all habitats. However, all five species recorded in the mangrove forest sites were also observed in the successional forest sites.

Figure 2. Representative specimens of myxomycetes collected from successional forest sites, (A) *Craterium minutum* (B) *Cribraria microcarpa*, (C) *Diachea leucopodia*, and from coastal mangrove forest sites, (D) *Arcyria cinerea*, (E) *Physarum oblatum*, (F) *Stemonitis fusca*, scale bar = 1.5 mm.

Discussion

Despite the increasing number of publications related to myxomycetes in the last decade, the Philippines has still many habitats or areas that has not been explored for myxomycetes (Dagamac and dela Cruz 2019), which is particularly true for many sites in the Visayas and the Mindanao region. Even simple surveys of documenting the assemblages of myxomycetes in these regions are relatively few. In fact, most myxomycete surveys in the country were carried out on areas in Luzon Island, on the northern part of the Philippines (see studies of dela Cruz et al. 2011, 2014; Viray et al. 2015; Dagamac et al. 2012, 2014; Bernardo et al. 2018; Policina and dela Cruz 2020b).

Figure 3. Venn diagram of shared and exclusive myxomycetes between successional forest sites [AY, LP] and coastal mangrove forest sites [TJ, TG].

Taxonomic studies in the Visayas islands included those carried out by Alfaro et al. (2014) which reported myxomycetes in Negros Occidental and by Macabago et al. (2017) in Bohol Island. Our rapid survey of myxomycetes in Negros Oriental, the sister province of Negros Occidental, therefore would add to the pool of myxomycete data available for Negros Island, and overall for the Visayas region. Our study may have recovered a less number of species (=19) in comparison to the studies in Negros Occidental (28 species, Alfaro et al. 2014) and Bohol (54 species, Macabago et al. 2017), but these comparisons were unlikely due to the different number of samples studied in each case.

In fact, the generated results in our study in Negros Oriental were slightly higher to the generated data in the study of Alfaro et al. (2014) in Negros Occidental. They recovered 28 species of myxomycetes from 450 MC, thereby resulting to a proportion value of 0.06 species per MC. The present study, with 19 species from 240 MC also resulted in a proportion value of 0.08 species per MC, implying that the recovery of myxomycetes in relation to the prepared MC is higher herein. However, both studies in Negros Island gave a significantly lower value in comparison to the results of Macabago et al. (2017) with a total of 54 species from 504 MC and a proportion value of 0.1 species per MC.

The significant increase in the myxomycetes recovered in Bohol Island may be attributed to various reasons. The number of moist chambers between the two islands were significantly different. As such, an unequal number of recovered species is expected. In the studies of dela Cruz et al. (2014) and Macabago et al. (2016), they highlighted how the number of moist chambers can influence the number of species recorded in a study. It is also worth noting that Macabago et al. (2017) surveyed seven different sites with varying vegetation types that are exposed to both natural, i.e., earthquakes and typhoons, and anthropogenic, i.e. tourist influx, disturbances. The relatively high anthropogenic events that occurred in Bohol Island coupled by the recent natural disturbance during the time of collection may have structurally

and functionally altered the forest structure causing various effects such as an increase on the amount of available suitable microhabitats for myxomycetes on the forest floor. This may have played an important part on the higher number of myxomycete species recorded in Bohol Island.

Cabutaje et al. (2021) similarly noted how a recent typhoon has resulted in a higher number of myxomycetes. Previous ecological works may also explain this outcome. Habitat loss and forest disturbance in southwestern Peruvian Amazon showed a strong effect on the assemblages of myxomycetes (Rojas and Stephenson 2013). The same pattern was also observed in several studies conducted in the country where disturbed areas displayed a higher myxomycete species richness and diversity (Dagamac et al. 2015a, 2015c; Bernardo et al. 2018; Eloreta et al. 2020) and therefore, may have followed the intermediate disturbance hypothesis. Interestingly, Bohol Island, the 10th largest island in the Philippines with a land area of 3 864 km², is three times smaller than Negros Island, and yet reported more species of myxomycetes. While any assumptions on the possible effect of island size to myxomycetes cannot be deduced at this point, this concept would be an interesting topic for future studies.

Our study added six species of myxomycetes for the Negros Island, thereby bringing the number of species known in region to a total of 40. Comparing the collecting localities, Ayungon successional forest site, characterized as a mountainous forest with extensive reforestation efforts, yielded 13 taxa, but still considerably lower than the comparable results in heterogenous mountain forest sites in Negros (Mt. Kanlaon, 27 species, Alfaro et al. 2014) and Bohol (Raja Sikatuna, 24 species, Macabago et al. 2017). On the other hand, Liptong (LP) woodland, a true successional forest planted mainly with native and hardwood trees in a privately-owned land, had 13 species but differed in composition with 7 species shared by the two inland forests (Fig. 3), and six species unique to each site.

The recorded number is likewise comparable to the number of taxa recovered from a monotypic, man-made forest in Bohol, also with 13 species (Macabago et al. 2017), but with only two shared species with this study – *Collaria arcyryonema* and *Physarum oblatum*. With the number of species recovered in the present study, we provided additional evidence that successional forests are good habitats for myxomycetes and follow successional stages where the peak of species can be found thriving and proliferating, thereby corroborating results from areas for which proofs of high myxomycete diversity was observed even after a disturbance brought by natural calamities (i.e., earthquake, volcanic eruptions, and typhoon [Macabago et al. 2017; Isagan et al. 2020; Cabutaje et al. 2021]).

Interestingly, one forest ecosystem with distinct environmental conditions and vegetation, the mangrove forests, may potentially host many unique assemblages of myxomycetes, but has remained largely unexplored. Early surveys of mangrove-associated myxomycetes were mostly conducted in Brazil (Cavalcanti et al. 2000; Damasceno et al. 2011; Agra et al. 2015; Cavalcanti et al. 2016). The Philippines with more than 250,000 hectares of mangrove forests (Long and Giri 2011) is ideal for comparative surveys of mangrove-associated myxomycetes. The first and only report of myxomycetes in mangroves in the Philippines was that of a short note published by Savillo (2015) wherein only a single taxon, *Lycogala conicum*, was reported on a dead branch of a living mangrove tree.

The present study has recovered seven specimens (albeit five singletons) in either or both of the collecting locations. In the previous study of Cavalcanti et al. (2016) in Brazil, their two expeditions in three sites to collect field specimens and substrates for culture preparation recovered 21 specimens belonging to 11 species. Furthermore, the earlier study of Trierveiler-Pereira et al. (2008) also documented three species. These reports as with our study consistently suggest a low abundance of myxomycetes in

coastal mangrove forests. The constant and direct exposure to high or moderate level of salinity and perhaps sunlight in coastal mangrove forests may be unfavorable for myxomycetes since they are often found sporulating in a forest ground with canopy cover and sufficient humidity (Stephenson 1989).

In fact, salinity is a crucial limiting factor on mangrove trees and affects its propagule germination, normal growth, and reproduction (Naidoo 2006). This could also restrict the myxomycetes to develop and complete its life cycle, particularly the germination of the spores and/or the ability of plasmodium to reach the stage of fructification. The influence of salinity on myxomycete development in mangrove forest sites therefore warrants further systematic experimental study. Another factor to consider in explaining the low abundance of myxomycetes in mangrove forests is the availability of plant litter. Data from previous studies demonstrated that vegetational structure, with consideration on substrates availability, strongly influences myxomycete occurrence (Rojas and Doss 2014).

In the Philippines, a number of studies along coastal areas but with mixed plant communities recorded a relatively higher number of species (Macabago et al. 2012, 2017; Cabutaje et al. 2021). Ecological evidences from other studies also supported the notion of vegetation with high plant heterogeneity is associated with a higher number of myxomycete species and diversity (Dagamac et al. 2015c) than those with homogenous vegetation (Carascal et al. 2017; Redeña-Santos et al. 2017, Macabago et al. 2017). In mangrove ecosystems, available microhabitats where myxomycetes can sporulate would be limited to fallen twigs, leaf litter, and fallen logs from mangrove tree species and some additional plant litter from a minimal number of other plants (Agra et al. 2015). Taken this altogether, the vegetation and the presence of less suitable microhabitats in mangrove sites may have possibly influence the low myxomycete occurrence in mangrove forests. But as noted above, these ideas still requires further verification. What is clear from our study is the update in the number of species of myxomycetes recorded in mangroves in the country, now total to six species – *Lycogala conicum*, *Didymium nigripes*, *Lamproderma scintillans*, *Arcyria cinerea*, *Stemonitis fusca*, and *Physarum oblatum*.

In terms of the relative abundance, the most abundant species we recorded in our study, *D. nigripes*, *S. fusca* and *D. effusum*, were also recorded as either abundant or common in Negros Occidental and Bohol in the Visayas region (Alfaro et al. 2014; Macabago et al. 2017). The same pattern of species occurrence was also noted in other forest sites in the Philippines (Pecundo et al. 2020). Another commonly encountered species, *A. cinerea*, has been reported abundant in various substrates including grass litter (Carascal et al. 2017), dried inflorescences (Pecundo et al. 2017), and tree barks (Policina and dela Cruz 2020a), and in varied ecosystems, i.e., ultramafic forest (Rea-Maminta et al. 2015), coastal forest sites (Dagamac et al. 2015a; Cabutaje et al. 2021), island and islets (Macabago et al. 2012; Kuhn et al. 2013; Macabago et al. 2020a), and lowland and highland mountainous forest sites (Cheng et al. 2013; Dagamac et al. 2015b, 2015c; Eloreta et al. 2020). *A. cinerea* has also been recorded as a mangrove-associated myxomycete (Cavalcanti et al. 2014). In addition, *Stemonitis fusca* and *C. arcyronema* were also previously recorded from several mangrove sites in Brazil (Damasceno et al. 2011; Cavalcanti et al. 2014, 2016), suggesting their ubiquitous distribution and/or potential adaptation to mangrove environments. The other myxomycetes that were either exclusive or unique to the woodland or successional forests in this study were recorded in other forest types in the country (Dagamac et al. 2015b; Pecundo et al. 2020). In summary, the present study provided baseline data on the myxomycetes of Negros Island and the Visayas

region. It has updated the number of species recorded in the region. It also reported for the first time five species of myxomycetes associated with Philippine mangroves.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to express its sincerest gratitude to the Department of Environment and Natural Resources - Negros Island Regional Office (DENR-NIR) for granting the permit to work in Ayungon forest and the DENR Community Environment and Natural Resources Office (CENRO) for their assistance during the expedition in Ayungon forest. We also express our gratitude to the graduate students of the Fungal Biodiversity, Ecogenomics and Systematics (FBeS) group, especially Enrico Cabutaje and Nikki Heherson Dagamac, for their assistance in the identification of the myxomycetes described herein and the Research Center for Natural and Applied Sciences (RCNAS) for the use of the facilities and research grant.

References

- Agra LANN, Bezerra ACC, Cavalcanti LH. 2015. Myxomycetes from mangroves: species occurring in the state of Maranhão, northeastern Brazil. *Braz J Biol.* 75: 222-227.
- Alfaro JR, Alcayde DL, Agbulos JB, Dagamac NH, dela Cruz TEE. 2014. The occurrence of myxomycetes from a lowland montane forest and agricultural plantations of Negros Occidental, Western Visayas, Philippines. *Fine Focus* 1(1): 7-20.
- Bernardo JLM, Arioder JLQ, Almadrones-Reyes KJ, Dagamac NHA. 2018. Myxomycetes communities occurring in fragmented forest patches in two municipalities of Laguna, Philippines. *Community Ecol.* 19: 289-299.
- Cabutaje EM, Pecundo MH, dela Cruz TEE. 2021. Diversity of myxomycetes in typhoon-prone areas: a case study in beach and inland forests of Aurora and Quezon Province, Philippines. *Sydowia* 73: 113-132.
- Carascal M, Rea MAD, Dagamac NHA, dela Cruz TEE. 2017. Myxomycetes associated with grassland litter in the Philippines. *Curr Res Environ Appl Mycol.* 7: 56-63.
- Cavalcanti LH, Bezerra ACC, Campos EL. 2000. Diversidade da mixobiota de Manguezais. In *Mangrove 2000. Sustainable use of estuaries and mangroves: Challenges and prospects*, Universidade Federal Rural de Pernambuco, ISME - International Society for Mangrove Ecosystems, Brazil. p. 44-54.
- Cavalcanti LH, Damasceno G, Bezerra ACC, Costa AAA. 2014. Mangrove myxomycetes: species occurring on *Conocarpus erectus* L. (Combretaceae). *Sydowia* 66(2): 183-190.
- Cavalcanti Ld, Damasceno G, Costa AAA, Bezerra ACC. 2016. Myxomycetes in Brazilian mangroves: species associated with *Avicennia nitida*, *Laguncularia racemosa* and *Rhizophora mangle*. *Mar Biodivers Rec.* 9: 31.
- Cheng CBT, Yu KNT, Campos ML, Adora JMV, Pascua GCP, Pangilinan MVB, Buaya AT, dela Cruz TEE. 2013. Occurrence and diversity of myxomycetes (plasmodial slime molds) along the northern slope of Mt. Makulot, Cuenca, Batangas, Philippines. *J Asia Pac Biodivers.* 4: 65-83.

- Dagamac NHA, Stephenson SL, dela Cruz TEE. 2012. Occurrence, distribution and diversity of myxomycetes (plasmodial slime moulds) along two transects in Mt. Arayat National Park, Pampanga, Philippines. *Mycology* 3(2): 119-126.
- Dagamac NH, Stephenson SL, dela Cruz TEE. 2014. The occurrence of litter Myxomycetes at different elevations in Mt. Arayat National Park, Pampanga, Philippines. *Nova Hedwigia* 98(1-2): 187-196.
- Dagamac NHA, Rea-Maminta MAD, Batungbacal NS, Jung SH, Bulang CRT, dela Cruz TEE. 2015a. Diversity of plasmodial slime molds (myxomycetes) on coastal, mountain, and community forests of Puerto Galera, Oriental Mindoro, Philippines. *J Asia Pac Biodivers.* 8: 322-329.
- Dagamac NHA, Rea-Maminta MAD, dela Cruz TEE. 2015b. Plasmodial slime molds of a tropical karst forest, Quezon National Park, Philippines. *Pac Sci.* 69: 411-422.
- Dagamac NHA, dela Cruz TEE, Rea-Maminta MAD, Aril-dela Cruz JV, Schnittler M. 2015c. Rapid assessment of myxomycete diversity in the Bicol Peninsula, Philippines. *Nova Hedwigia* 104 (1-3): 31-46.
- Dagamac NHA, dela Cruz TEE. 2019. The Philippine slime molds after Dogma's 1975 list – How far have we been? *Philipp J Syst Biol.* 13: 58-65.
- Damasceno G, Tenório JCG, Cavalcanti LH. 2011. Stemonitaceae (Myxomycetes) in Brazilian mangroves. *Sydowia* 63: 9-22.
- dela Cruz TEE, Kuhn RV, Javier AOM, Rodillas CP, Parra CM, Corpuz LHM, McHugh RD. 2011. Occurrence and distribution of plasmodial myxomycetes in Hundred Islands National Park, Pangasinan, Philippines. *Acta Manil.* 59: 65-74.
- dela Cruz TEE, Rea MAD, Tran HTM, Ko Ko TW, Stephenson SL. 2014. A comparative species listing of myxomycetes from tropical (Philippines) and temperate (United States) forests. *Mycosphere* 5: 299-311.
- Eloreta MFBM, Policina MS, dela Cruz TEE. 2020. Occurrence and diversity of myxomycetes along the forest edges of Mt. Isarog Natural Park, Camarines Sur, Philippines. *Curr Res Environ Appl Mycol.* 10: 377-385.
- Isagan MDE, Carbonell MKC, Dalangin YA, Lapira AJL, Pecundo MH, dela Cruz TEE. 2020. Species listing and diversity of myxomycetes from Mt. Makulot and Napayong Island in Taal Lake, Batangas, Philippines. *MycoAsia* 2020/05.
- Kuhn RV, Javier AOM, Rodillas CP, Parra CM, Corpuz LHM, Moron LS, dela Cruz TEE. 2013. Diversity of plasmodial myxomycetes from Anda Island, Pangasinan, Philippines. *Biotropia* 20: 1-9.
- Long JB, Giri C. 2011. Mapping the Philippines' mangrove forests using Landsat imagery. *Sens.* 11(3): 2972-2981.
- Leontyev DV. 2010. Myxomycetes from genera *Stemonitis*, *Stemonitopsis* and *Stemonaria* in Ukraine: identification and distribution. *Mikol.* 44(55): 398-409.

- Macabago SAB, dela Cruz TEE, Stephenson SL. 2012. First records of myxomycetes from Lubang Island, Occidental Mindoro, Philippines. *Sydowia* 64: 109-118.
- Macabago SAB, dela Cruz TEE. 2014. Preservation and enzyme production of myxomycetes from Lubang Island, Occidental Mindoro, Philippines. *Philipp Sci Lett.* 7(2): 331-336.
- Macabago SAB, Stephenson SL, dela Cruz TEE. 2016. Diversity and distribution of myxomycetes in coastal and mountain forests of Lubang Island, Occidental Mindoro, Philippines. *Mycosphere* 7(1): 18-29.
- Macabago SA, Dagamac NH, dela Cruz TE, Stephenson SL. 2017. Implications of the role of dispersal on the occurrence of litter-inhabiting myxomycetes in different vegetation types after a disturbance: a case study in Bohol Islands, Philippines. *Nova Hedwigia* 104(1-3): 221-236.
- Macabago SAB, dela Cruz TEE, Stephenson SL. 2020a. Myxomycetes of Coron Island and additions to the Myxomycetes of Palawan group of islands in the Philippines. *Karstenia* 58(2): 157-167.
- Macabago SAB, Dagamac NHA, dela Cruz TEE, Stephenson S. 2020b. Myxomycetes of the Caramoan Islands and an update on the species found in the Bicol Peninsula, Philippines. *Philipp J Syst Biol.* 14(1): 1-9.
- Naidoo G. 2006. Factors contributing to dwarfing in the mangrove *Avicennia marina*. *Ann Bot-London* 97: 1095-1101.
- Pecundo MH, Dagamac NHA, Stephenson SL, dela Cruz TEE. 2017. First myxomycetes survey in the limestone forest of Puerto Princesa Subterranean River National Park, Palawan, Philippines. *Nova Hedwigia* 104: 129-141.
- Pecundo MH, Dagamac NHA, dela Cruz TEE. 2020. A comparative diversity study of myxomycetes in the lowland forests of Mt. Malasimbo and Mt. Siburan, Mindoro Island, Philippines. *Karstenia* 58 (2): 275-291.
- Policina MS, dela Cruz TEE. 2020a. Records of corticolous myxomycetes from selected trees in Angat Watershed Forest Reserve, Bulacan, Philippines. *Philipp J Syst Biol.* 14(3): 1-6.
- Policina MS, dela Cruz TEE. 2020b. Influence of cardinal directions on corticolous myxomycetes associated with *Swietenia macrophylla* King. *Karstenia* 58(2): 201-214.
- Rea-Maminta MAD, Dagamac NHA, Huyop FZ, Wahab RA, dela Cruz TEE. 2015. Comparative diversity and heavy metal biosorption of myxomycetes from forest patches on ultramafic and volcanic soils. *Chem Ecol.* 31: 741-753.
- Redeña-Santos JC, Dunca JAU, Duong VT, Dagamac NHA. 2017. Myxomycetes occurring on selected agricultural leaf litter. *Studies in Fungi* 2: 171-177.
- Rojas C, Stephenson SL. 2013. Effect of forest disturbance on myxomycete assemblages in the southwestern Peruvian Amazon. *Fungal Divers.* 59:45-53.
- Rojas C, Doss RG. 2014. Does habitat loss affect tropical myxomycetes? *Mycosphere* 5(5): 688–696.

- Savillo I. 2015. A short note: *Lycogala* spp. in mangroves: An update and an introduction to Foliimortuous myxomycetes. *J Wetl Biodiversity* 5: 47-49.
- Stephenson SL. 1989. Distribution of myxomycetes in temperate forests, II. Patterns of occurrence of bark surface of living trees, leaf litter, and dung. *Mycologia* 81(4): 608-621.
- Stephenson SL, Stempen H. 1994. *Myxomycetes: A handbook of slime molds*. Timber Press, Portland, Oregon.
- Tran H, Stephenson S, Pollock E. 2015. Evaluation of *Physarum polycephalum* plasmodial growth and lipid production using rice bran as a carbon source. *BMC Biotechnol.* 15(1): 67.
- Trierveiler-Pereira L, Baltazar JM, Loguercio-Leite C. 2008. Santa Catarina Island mangroves 1 - First report of myxomycetes on *Avicennia schaueriana*. *Mycotaxon* 103: 145-152.
- Viray AT, Rotap DDS, Migraso LL, Sibbaluca NCL, Escobar AB, dela Cruz TEE. 2015. Occurrence and diversity of myxomycetes (slime molds) in Polillo Island, Quezon Province, Philippines. *Acta Manil.* 62: 09-17.